

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Clark/Regan (2016): Mass Mobilization Project (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/4E6A40FF-4AE0-4CC8-89B3-DBE162BE07C0>

Abstract

The Mass Mobilization Project is a project by David H. Clark and Patrick M. Regan, funded by the Political Instability Task Force. It covers 10.000+ anti-government protests from around the globe (162 countries) (3) in the time period from 1990-2020, with the latest version update including formerly missing notes for 2700+ cases (2). This dataset provides descriptions on the happenings at protest events against governments as well as information on the protester demands and government responses (Clark & Regan 2015: 2). They aim to include any protest event that targets (a) countries own) government with at least 50 participants, while excluding (a) inter-communal demonstrations, as these do not target the government, (b) rebel attacks or other armed protests, since they are no longer an expression of demand for change but rather a means of acquiring said change by force and (c) political rallies as these are considered a pro-state action (Clark & Regan 2015: 3-4). Lexis-Nexis was utilized as the source of information. It was used to search for newspaper reports while focusing on four major publications: The New York Times, the Washington Post, the Christian Science Monitor and the Times of London (Clark & Regan 2015: 2-3). Of the 17.000+ total entries in this dataset, there are over 1.500+ events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data. As of summer 2024, it is not clear whether work on the data collection is continuing. The data review includes both a link to the official Mass Mobilization Project website as well as a link to the Harvard Dataverse website from which both the dataset and the Mass Mobilization Data Project Codebook and User's Manual are available for download.

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Data Review – Mass Mobilization Project

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Lexis-Nexis was utilized as the source of information. It was used to search for newspaper reports while focusing on four major publications: The New York Times, the Washington Post, the Christian Science Monitor and the Times of London. With the exception of the MENA region for which the paper Jerusalem Post was included on top of the other four publications. The search for reports within these sources then continued with searching for each country in the dataset year by year while looking for the terms: Protest, demonstration, riot and mass mobilization. If more than a hundred entries were listed under these search conditions, the researchers would proceed to code these events. If however that was not the case, then the search was expanded to include other sources such as regional papers and wire-reports (Clark & Regan 2015: 2-3).

The variables used during the coding process include the following: the country name (as well as its database country code), the year and region as well as whether a protest occurred in a particular period or not. Then if a protest did take place, the following factors were analyzed: the start and end date of said protest, whether protester violence occurred but not what kind, the location and the number of participants (as well as a categorical indicator) and their protest groups identity. The issue protesters were campaigning about is listed as the variable "protester demands", of which seven categories were identified, which include: labor or wage dispute, land tenure or farm issues, police brutality or arbitrary actions, political behavior/processes, price increases or tax policy, removal of corrupt or reviled political person and lastly social restrictions. Similarly, the variable "state response" can also be divided into seven categories including: the accommodation of demands, arrests, beatings, crowd dispersal mechanics, ignoring, killings and shootings. The last variable "sources, notes" provides both the original sources of information as well as any information that might have been relevant for coding decisions and notes on the happenings at the protest in question (Clark & Regan 2015: 3-6).

On the Mass Mobilization Data website in the “Visualization” section, the data can be approached via three different trends: World trends, regional trends and country trends. In the “World Trends” section the user is able to choose the year they are interested in and will see all protest documented in that year in the form of an interactive map. In the “Regional Trends” section the user can choose their region of interest (all the continents as well as MENA and Oceania) and a time period that is supposed to be depicted. Three bar charts will be generated: one showing the total protest duration in days for each year, one showing the frequency of demands for each year (here the user can filter for each category listed under the variable “protester demands”), and finally one showing the frequency of violence (here the user can filter for “Nonviolent”, “Protester Violence”, “State Violence” and “Both Violence”). Lastly, the “Country Trends” section is structured in the exact same way as the “Regional Trends” section. The only difference being that the bar charts will focus on a chosen country instead of an entire region (5).

Mackey writes: “*We urge scholars to seek uses of the Mass Mobilization data that incorporate the possibility of temporal changes; we also urge scholars to develop theories to explain that change over time.*” He then shows some example analyses using the Bayesian changepoint methods to prove that by using this dataset differences in protest behaviour and state response over time, as well as the designated changing point can be calculated (4).

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Number of Entries
Armenia	108
Azerbaijan	132
Belarus	80
GDR	11
Georgia	67
Estonia	64
Kazakhstan	93
Kyrgyzstan	173
Latvia	98
Lithuania	53
Moldova	114

Russia	205
Tajikistan	51
Turkmenistan	31
Ukraine	157
USSR	60
Uzbekistan	55
Total Entries	1552

Sources:

- (1) Mass Mobilization Project. Explore the Mass Mobilization Data. <https://massmobilization.github.io/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (2) Clark, David H. and Patrick M. Regan. 2015. Mass Mobilization Data Project Codebook and User's Manual. Available for download here: <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.7910/DVN/HTTWYL>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (3) Mass Mobilization Project. About the Mass Mobilization Project. <https://massmobilization.github.io/about.html>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (4) Mackey, Kyle. Analysis of Changepoints in Mass Mobilization Data <https://massmobilization.github.io/mmChangepoint.html>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (5) Mass Mobilization Analytics https://massmobilization.shinyapps.io/mm_analytics/. Last accessed 27.09.2024.